

Study on Osmotic Dehydration of Kale (*Brassica Oleracea*) and Its Application in Beverage Development

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ABSTRACT

Osmotic dehydration is a technique that retains the nutritional attributes of the perishable food products especially vegetables and enhances their shelf life. This phenomenon is eco-friendly and is used to remove the water content leading to increased storage capacity. Kale is a leafy green vegetable that has gained attention of the scientific community due to its high content of bioactive compounds and health-promoting phytochemicals. The present study was undertaken to investigate the effect of two osmotic agents; NaCl and Sucrose in 1:1 ratio in combination with dehydration on the proximate and mineral composition of selected vegetable. Further the study focussed on formulation and sensory appraisal of juices prepared from kale. The proximate composition (Moisture, Ash, Protein, Fat, Fibre and Carbohydrates) was analysed by standard procedures given by AOAC and minerals were determined by AAS. The findings showed osmotic agents with 40° Brix significantly increased Ash (3.73 ± 0.05), Fat (0.7 ± 0.3) and Fibre (9.28 ± 0.02) while 70° Brix significantly increased Protein (2.28 ± 0.12) and Carbohydrate (9.73 ± 0.17) content. While mineral content determination showed osmotic agents with 70° Brix significantly increased all minerals except Iodine. Furthermore, kale juice with 60% concentration had significantly higher scores in sensory evaluation as compared to other variants. Thus, the current study recommends application of osmotic dehydration technique that results in reduced moisture content, leading to longer shelf life and enhancing the quality attributes indicating its multirole consumption, moreover the study also suggests that kale is a healthy choice for consumption that can be included into human diet.

Keywords: Kale, Phytochemicals, Antioxidants, Osmotic Dehydration, Perishable, Eco-friendly, Osmotic agent

1. Introduction

Because of their nutritional benefits, consumers today have a greater need for wholesome meals like fresh fruits and vegetables than they had a few decades ago (Aneja *et al.*, 2014). Vitamins and minerals are abundant in vegetables (Aybüke *et al.*, 2021). These are included in dietary guidelines and are recommended to be included in the diet by experts due to the high concentrations of vitamins C and A, minerals, dietary fiber, electrolytes, and phytochemicals, including antioxidants (Slavin *et al.*, 2012). Consuming fresh vegetables is good for human health, and because of their high nutritional content, they have been used for a variety of purposes. Vegetables' high water content is the primary factor contributing to their perishability. Numerous techniques or combinations of techniques have been tried to extend the shelf life of these. One of the best and most appropriate ways to extend the shelf life of vegetables is through osmotic dehydration. A semi-permeable membrane causes water to be removed from lower solute concentrations to higher concentrations, creating an equilibrium state on both sides of the membrane. The water is removed at a low temperature, which significantly extends the food product's shelf life (Yadav and Singh *et al.*, 2014). This

method has attracted a lot of interest since it preserves the natural qualitative characteristics of raw materials while also reducing the amount of drying energy required. Furthermore, as previous researchers have noted, this technique provides a cost-effective and environmentally responsible way to preserve food (Hassan *et al.*, 2024). Their vitamin and mineral content, color, flavor, and ability to retain taste make this technique superior to others. Because of its rich nutritional and mineral content, kale is becoming more and more popular among those who are concerned about their health. It is known as "Cabbage's cousin" and is a lord of green vegetables, close to undomesticated cabbage. According to botany, it is *Brassica oleracea* var. *acephala*, a leafy vegetable that is harvested in the fall and winter (Wu *et al.*, 2022), a member of the *Cruciferae/Brassicaceae* family (Tiwari *et al.*, 2020), and it contains a range of constitutional metabolites (Hahn *et al.*, 2016). Kale is a high source of vitamin C, which speeds up its antioxidant action. It is also rich in vitamin B complex and vitamin E, which have several health benefits, such as helping with Beri-Beri, healthy skin and hair, brain development, and erythrocyte growth. Kale's protein and amino acid levels are crucial for cell repair and bodily growth (Choudhury *et al.*, 2022). The antioxidant and free radical scavenging qualities are attributed to phenolic substances (kaempferol, quercetin, and isorhamnetin), flavonoids (glycosylated flavanols), and glucosinolates. According to Raiola *et al.*, (2018), the Brassicaceae family has beneficial cardiovascular protective functions that help prevent gastrointestinal tract cancer. Green kale, dwarf kale, marrow-stem kale, tronchuda kale, curly leaf kale, Scotch kale, tree kale, and bore kale are among the various types of kale that are sold on the market (Satheesh *et al.*, 2020). Due to the presence of bioactive phytochemicals, kale has been used extensively in traditional medicine around the world to prevent and treat a variety of illnesses, such as liver ailments, excessive cholesterol, hyperglycaemia, rheumatism and stomach ulcers. It is a noteworthy supply of vital minerals that are crucial for metabolic activities, such as potassium, sodium, zinc, calcium, iron, magnesium, and phosphorus (Korus, 2020).

Given its medicinal potential, the current study was designed to ascertain the nutritional makeup of kale and create "juices" using oranges, coriander and mint in order to assess consumer acceptability.

2. Materials and Methods

- **Raw material, Reagents and Chemicals:** Fresh Kale was procured from local market, Faridabad, Haryana. Other materials that were used in the study (Coriander, Mint leaves, Oranges) were procured from Banasthali Vidyapith. All chemicals and reagents utilized in this study were of analytical grade.
- **Sample preparation:** 1 kg of fresh kale vegetable was weighed and was washed and cleaned with distilled water 3 to 4 times to remove dirt, contaminants and extraneous materials including damaged leaves. Then, they were chopped evenly for further processing as shown in Fig 1 and Fig 2. They were then stored in proper storage conditions for further use.

Fig 1: Fresh vegetable

Fig 2: Pre-processed vegetable

- **Design of the experiment:** The pre-processed vegetable samples were divided in 4 different proportions and were labelled as; the first sample acted as control or fresh sample that underwent no specific treatment was labelled as FV. Second sample labelled as OD1 was treated at 50° brix for immersion time 60 mins. Third sample labelled as OD2 was treated at 40° brix for immersion time 80 mins. Fourth sample labelled as OD3 was treated at 70° brix for immersion time 90 mins with hot air drying for 6 hrs at 40°C for all the three osmotically treated samples.
- **Osmotic Dehydration Treatment of vegetable samples:** The osmotic solutions were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of osmotic agent including Sucrose and NaCl in 1:1 ratio in distilled water.

FV (S1)	Control (fresh sample with no treatment)
OD1 (S2)	50° brix for immersion time 60 mins with hot air drying for 6 hrs at 40°C
OD2 (S3)	40° brix for immersion time 80 mins with hot air drying for 6 hrs at 40°C
OD3 (S4)	70° brix for immersion time 90 mins with hot air drying for 6 hrs at 40°C

After the treatment, the samples were removed from the solution and were rinsed with distilled water. The treated samples were spread evenly on stainless steel tray and these were placed in hot air oven at pre-set conditions. Subsequently, these samples were packed on air tight zip lock polyethylene bags and were stored at room temperature for further usage.

Sample 1 (OD1)

Sample 2 (OD2)

Sample 3 (OD3)

Fig 3: Application of Osmotic Dehydration Technique on Kale vegetable

Sample 1 (OD1)

Sample 2 (OD2)

Sample 3 (OD3)

Fig 4: Osmotic Dehydrated Kale vegetable

- **Determination of Proximate Composition:** The proximate analysis was done for Moisture, Ash, Protein, Fat and Fibre by standard methods given by AOAC, 2023 and carbohydrate was calculated by difference method.
- **Determination of Mineral Content:** The minerals analysis was done for- Iron, Calcium, Potassium, Sodium and Phosphorous were estimated by Atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) method (AOAC, 2023). Concisely, 0.5 g of vegetable sample powder was accurately taken and transferred into Teflon digestion tubes. To each tube, 5 mL of nitric acid was added, and the mixture was vortexed for 30 s. The tubes were then placed in a preheated microwave digester and subjected to digestion at 120 °C for 5 min. After digestion, the tubes were cooled to room temperature and diluted with 50 mL of distilled water.
- **Development of Juices:** Juices were developed by incorporating kale, herbal extract and orange juice in different proportions (Table 1).

Table 1: Composition of Juices from Kale Vegetable

Product Code	Orange Juice (ml)	Herbal Extract* (ml)	Kale Juice (ml)
A1	25	15	60
A2	20	15	65
A3	15	15	70
A4	10	15	75

*Herbal Extract = Black and White salt (1:1) + Corriander leaves, Mint leaves and Citric Acid (1:1:1)

- **Sensory Evaluation:** Sensory evaluation of formulated juices was performed by using 9-point hedonic scale (ranging from like extremely to dislike extremely) (Yadav *et al.*, 2024). The sensory attributes for juices evaluation included Aroma, Color, Taste, Texture, Appearance, Aftertaste and Overall Acceptability. The evaluation was carried out by 30 semi-trained panel members who were from Food Science and Nutrition department and were aged between 20- 30 years.
- **Statistical Analysis:** The IBM SPSS Statistics software (version 20) was used to statistically interpret the data. The triplicate determinations of Mean \pm Standard Deviation (SD), One-Way ANOVA, Least Significance Difference (LSD) were used to express the results of the study.

3. Results and Discussion

- **Proximate composition:** Table 2 shows the proximate composition of Fresh and Osmotic dehydrated leaves of Kale vegetable. The results indicated that moisture content of treated samples of kale vegetable significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) decreased signifying longer shelf life while other nutrients ash, protein, fat, fiber and carbohydrate significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) increased upon the application of dehydration treatment. Results of moisture content ranged from (79.9 ± 1.1 to 29.7 ± 0.08). It was seen highest in fresh sample and lowest in OD2 sample. Almost all osmotic dehydrated samples contain moisture; therefore, its determination is crucial for several microbiological and chemical processes as moisture content significantly affects food quality, freshness and microbiological resistance (Zambrano *et al.*, 2019). These results were in accordance with findings of (Emebu and Anyika, 2011) who observed moisture content in fresh kale vegetable to be 81.30%. Agarwal *et al.*, 2017 found that moisture content in Kale vegetable was (9.08 ± 0.6) which was contrary to results of the present study. Result of ash content ranged from (3.73 ± 0.05 to 3.03 ± 0.09), which highest in OD2 sample and lowest in fresh sample. Food product's ash content, an inorganic element, is a crucial component of their quality and indicates the presence of minerals (Ismail, 2017). These results were in line with the findings of (Agarwal *et al.*, 2017) who observed ash content in kale vegetable to be

4.34 ± 0.7. Emebu and Anyika, 2011 stated that 1.33% ash content which had significant difference from the present study. The results of protein content ranged from (2.28 ± 0.12 to 1.17 ± 0.09), highest observed in OD3 sample and lowest in fresh sample. The results of the present research were slightly low as compared to the findings of (Agarwal *et al.*, 2017) who observed (5.12 ± 0.43) protein content in kale vegetable. Emebu and Anyika, 2011 stated that 11.67% protein content which had significant difference from the present study. Results of fat content ranged from (0.7 ± 0.3 to 0.3 ± 0.05). It was seen highest in OD2 sample and lowest in fresh sample. A research concluded by (Agarwal *et al.*, 2017) found that fat content in Kale vegetable was (1.62 ± 0.3) which is higher as compared from the present study. Emebu and Anyika, 2011 stated that 0.26% fat content which had slight difference from the present study. Result of fibre content ranged from (9.28 ± 0.02 to 2.46 ± 0.01). It was seen highest in OD2 sample and lowest in fresh sample. Agarwal *et al.*, 2017 found that fibre content in Kale vegetable was (7.8 ± 0.42) which is lower as compared from the present study. Emebu and Anyika, 2011 stated that 3.0% fibre content which had significant difference from the present study. Result of carbohydrates content ranged from (9.73 ± 0.17 to 6.67 ± 0.05). It was seen highest in OD3 sample and lowest in fresh sample. Agarwal *et al.*, 2017 found that carbohydrate content in Kale vegetable was (7.8 ± 0.42) which is lower as compared from the present study. Emebu and Anyika, 2011 stated that 3.0% carbohydrate content which had significant difference from the present study. Overall investigation revealed that the Osmotic dehydration approach increases the nutritional content of vegetables by enriching them with vital nutrients, minerals, vitamins and polyphenols. It is simple, making it easier to process vegetables, saving energy, and enabling the cost-effective creation of dehydrated goods that preserve their natural qualities while boosting their nutritional content (Haneef *et al.*, 2024).

Table 2: Proximate composition of Fresh and Osmotic Dehydrated Kale vegetable samples

Nutrients (gm/100gm)	FV	OD1	OD2	OD3	F-value
Moisture	79.9 ± 1.1 bcd	32.2 ± 0.73 acd (67.8% ↓)	29.7 ± 0.08 abd (70.3% ↓)	37.5 ± 0.17 abc (62.5% ↓)	2505.32
Ash	3.03 ± 0.09 bc	3.53 ± 0.2 ^{ad} (96.47% ↑)	3.73 ± 0.05 ad (96.27% ↑)	3.2 ± 0.08 bc (96.8% ↑)	13.37
Protein	1.17 ± 0.09 bd	1.61 ± 0.45 ad (90.39% ↑)	1.87 ± 0.05 d (98.13% ↑)	2.28 ± 0.12 abc (97.72% ↑)	18.001
Fat	0.3 ± 0.05 ^c	0.4 ± 0.1 ^c (99.6% ↑)	0.7 ± 0.3 ^{ab} (99.3% ↑)	0.6 ± 0.0 ^{ns} (99.4% ↑)	3.13
Fibre	2.46 ± 0.01 bcd	8.77 ± 0.05 acd (91.23% ↑)	9.28 ± 0.02 abd (90.72% ↑)	7.26 ± 0.1 abc (92.74% ↑)	6349.20
Carbohydrate	6.67 ± 0.05 bcd	8.42 ± 0.06 acd (91.58% ↑)	7.73 ± 0.12 abd (92.27% ↑)	9.73 ± 0.17 abc (90.27% ↑)	263.46

Each data is the mean ± SD of three replicates. F- Values are significant at P ≤ 0.001. Different letters (a-d) at different columns of each parameter denote significant difference between means (p ≤ 0.05).

*FV- Fresh Vegetable sample/ Control, OD1- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 1, OD2- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 2, OD3- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 3

Fig 3: Proximate content of Fresh and Osmotic Dehydrated Kale vegetable

- Mineral content:** Table 3 shows the mineral analysis of fresh, OD (osmotic dehydrated) leaves of Kale vegetable respectively. The results determined that minerals iron, calcium, potassium, sodium and phosphorous significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) increased while iodine content significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) decreased onto dehydration treatment application. Result of iron content ranged from (1.85 ± 0.01 to 1.14 ± 0.03). It was seen highest in OD3 sample and lowest in OD1. Agarwal *et al.*, 2017 found that iron content in Kale vegetable was (13.5 ± 0.4) which is quite higher as compared from the present study. Emebu and Anyika, 2011 stated that 8.94% iron content in kale vegetable which had significant difference from the present study. Result of calcium content ranged from (4.22 ± 0.11 to 1.79 ± 0.15). It was seen highest in OD3 sample and lowest in fresh sample. Korus, 2020 found that calcium content in Kale vegetable was (221 ± 17) which had significant difference from the present study. Emebu and Anyika, 2011 stated that 4.05% calcium content which was almost similar to the findings of present study. Result of potassium content ranged from (7.32 ± 0.7 to 4.98 ± 0.08). It was seen highest in OD3 sample and lowest in fresh sample. Korus (2020) found that potassium content in Kale vegetable was (429 ± 18) which had significant difference from findings of the present study. Emebu and Anyika, 2011 stated that 7.03% potassium content which has minor difference from the present study. Result of sodium content ranged from (29.5 ± 0.12 to 12.6 ± 0.16). It was seen highest in OD3 sample and lowest in fresh sample. Korus, 2020 found that sodium content in Kale vegetable was (8.48 ± 0.14) which had significant difference as compared to the present study. Emebu and Anyika, 2011 stated that 4.69% sodium content which had significant difference from the present study. Result of phosphorous content ranged from (3.5 ± 0.16 to 1.8 ± 0.08). It was seen highest in OD3 sample and lowest in fresh sample. Korus, 2020 found that phosphorous content in Kale vegetable was (70.9 ± 1.4) which had significant difference as compared from the present study. Another study concluded that 92mg/100g phosphorous content was found in kale vegetable which had significant difference from the present study (Šamec *et al.*, 2018; Reda *et al.*, 2020). The presence of low concentrations of iodine is often associated with beneficial effects on plant growth, production and resilient, whereas adverse effects are noted when applying iodine at high concentrations (Kiferle *et al.*, 2021; Incrocci *et al.*, 2019). Result of iodine content ranged from (3.53 ± 0.12 to 2.41 ± 0.08). It was seen highest in fresh sample

and lowest in OD3 sample. Krzemińska *et al.*, 2024 found that iodine content in Kale vegetable was (178.49 ± 23.68) which had significant difference as compared from the present study. Overall investigation revealed that the Osmotic dehydration approach increases the nutritional content of vegetables by enriching them with vital nutrients, minerals, vitamins and polyphenols. It is simple, making it easier to process vegetables, saving energy, and enabling the cost-effective creation of dehydrated goods that preserve their natural qualities while boosting their nutritional content (Haneef *et al.*, 2024).

Table 3: Mineral content Analysis of Fresh and Osmotic Dehydrated Kale vegetable samples

Minerals (mg/100g)	FV	OD1	OD2	OD3	F- value
Iron	1.16 ± 0.16^{cd}	1.14 ± 0.03^{cd} (98.86% ↓)	1.66 ± 0.04^{ab} (98.34% ↑)	1.85 ± 0.01^{ab} (98.15% ↑)	31.41
Calcium	1.79 ± 0.15^{bcd}	3.26 ± 0.09^{acd} (96.74% ↑)	2.69 ± 0.13^{abd} (97.31% ↑)	4.22 ± 0.11^{abc} (95.78% ↑)	138.32
Potassium	4.98 ± 0.08^{bcd}	6.22 ± 0.05^{acd} (93.78% ↑)	5.77 ± 0.12^{abd} (94.23% ↑)	7.32 ± 0.7^{abc} (92.68% ↑)	240.66
Sodium	12.6 ± 0.16^{bcd}	22.7 ± 0.08^{acd} (77.3% ↑)	19.2 ± 0.08^{abd} (80.8% ↑)	29.5 ± 0.12^{abc} (70.5% ↑)	7176.36
Phosphorous	1.8 ± 0.08^{bcd}	2.7 ± 0.12^{acd} (97.3% ↑)	2.16 ± 0.04^{abd} (97.84% ↑)	3.5 ± 0.16^{abc} (96.5% ↑)	89.37
Iodine	3.53 ± 0.12^{bcd}	2.63 ± 0.12^a (97.37% ↓)	2.6 ± 0.08^a (97.4% ↓)	2.41 ± 0.08^a (97.59% ↓)	44.58

***FV**- Fresh Vegetable sample/ Control, **OD1**- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 1, **OD2**- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 2, **OD3**- Osmotic Dehydrated Vegetable sample 3

Each data is the mean \pm SD of three replicates. F- Values are significant at $P \leq 0.001$.

Different letters (a-d) at different columns of each parameter denote significant difference between means ($p \leq 0.05$).

Fig 4: Mineral Analysis of Fresh and Osmotic Dehydrated Kale vegetable

Sensory Evaluation: Sensory evaluation serves as an essential factor in understanding customers' feasible options and imbibing preferences. The sensory evaluation was done for developed juices which were made at different concentrations with a blend of Kale juice, Orange Juice and Herbal extract. A 9-point hedonic scale was used by the panel members for the evaluation under controlled conditions. Juice was freshly prepared prior to the evaluation procedure with the help of an electronic juicer grinder in the cooking lab of Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan. All the ingredients were cleaned and washed with distilled water 3 to 4 times to remove all dirt and dust particles to maintain hygiene and sanitation. Then, sensory evaluation of juices was done and each panel member was prior informed and consent was taken into consideration. Out of the juices with different concentrations, A2 was the most acceptable, having a composition as {100 ml Juice = 65 ml Kale juice + 20 ml Orange juice + 15 ml Herbal Extract}.

Fig 5: Sensory Evaluation and Acceptability of developed Kale juice

Fig 6: Sensory Evaluation and Acceptability of developed Kale juice

Table 4: Sensory Evaluation and Acceptability of developed Kale juice

Sample	Color	Appearance	Flavour	Consistency	Taste	Mouth Feel	Aftertaste	Overall Acceptability
Standard	8.6±0.7	8.5±0.6	8.4±0.6	8.1±0.9	8.3±0.7	8.3±0.7	8.1±0.8	8.4±0.6
A1	7.5±1.3*	7.4±1.2*	6±1.4*	6.8±1.4**	6.4±2.1*	6.2±1.8*	5.4±2.3*	6.3±2.0*
A2	7.6±1.1*	7.1±1.1**	6.1±2.0*	6.9±1.7**	6.2±2.1*	6.5±1.9*	5.8±2.6*	6.4±2.2*

A3	7.2±1.5*	6.9±1.2**	5.7±1.8*	6.8 ± 1.8**	5.5±2.2*	5.8±2.0*	4.9±2.3*	5.5±2.0*
A4	7.2±1.5*	6.8±1.1**	5.4±1.9*	6.5±1.7*	5.1±2.1*	5.2±2.2*	4.6±2.2*	5.2±2.0*

* - denotes significant difference and ** – denotes non- significant difference at different columns of each parameter denote significant difference between means ($p \leq 0.05$)

4. CONCLUSION

This research demonstrates that osmotic dehydration notably enhanced the attributes of dried leaves of kale vegetable. It effectively lowered moisture content, enhanced texture with reduced microbial load, leading to an elongated storability. The effect of osmotic dehydration reduced water activity and retards microbial extension by moisture removal and distorting the cell wall. In manufacturing unit, this process could be used to elevate shelf life of dehydrated vegetables by lowering the microbial load.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

It's not applicable.

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